

EMOTIONAL PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND SELF-CONCEPT OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN KIAMBU COUNTY, KENYA

BY

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ABSTRACT

Emotional parental involvement is believed to impact students' self-concept through various pathways: financial support, emotional support, academic engagement, guidance on social behaviours, and the modelling of self-acceptance and resilience. This study examined emotional parental involvement and self-concept of public secondary school students in Kiambu County, Kenya. The objective was to determine the influence of emotional parental involvement on the self-concept of public secondary school students in Kiambu County, Kenya. It employed a quantitative correlational research design. The target population was 3169 public secondary school students. Stratified and random sampling were used to select 355 students. Robson Self-Concept Scale (SCS) and the Parental Involvement Rating Scale (PIRS) were used to collect data. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and the research findings were displayed through tables. Findings showed a weak positive relationship between emotional involvement and self-concept ($r = 0.099$), ($p = 0.082$). This means that other factors could be responsible for the relationship between the variables. Further studies may be done to determine the association between emotional parental involvement and other possible predictors of self-concept.

Key words: Emotional, Parental Involvement, Self-concept, Secondary School, Students

INTRODUCTION

In China, Yi Yang et al (2021) found that high emotional involvement, such as warmth and intimacy, positively correlates with students' core self-evaluation, which includes self-esteem and self-efficacy. Emotional warmth has been demonstrated to boost self-concept, emotional intelligence, and subjective well-being, while rejection or overprotective parenting may have the opposite impact. According to Asio et al (2024), clearer and more solid self-views are made possible by secure parental attachment, which cultivates a sense of belonging and self-worth. G. Liu et al. (2017).

In this study, emotional involvement refers to a situation where parents actively support their children's emotional development and, provide a safe and nurturing environment where students feel understood, valued, and free to express their emotions. Self-concept on the other hand is how you view and regard oneself in relation to how others see you in your environment. The components of self-concept in this study include self-esteem, self-image, and ideal self.

Students are faced with lots of challenges which could be linked to psychological, environmental, and parental factors according to World Health Organization (WHO). The relationship between emotional parental involvement and self-concept among students is an area of interest in the field of psychology, owing to the possible positive contribution of emotional parental involvement in the growth and holistic development of students González and Aylward, (2021). Emotional parental involvement means that parents or caregivers invest in the general development of their children's emotional life. Self-concept is how one perceives oneself and how one views societal perception of oneself. Vaughn and Elmer (2020) argue that parental involvement is believed to impact students' self-concept through various pathways: emotional support, academic engagement, guidance on social behaviors, and the modeling of self-acceptance and resilience. According to Monisha et al (2024), involvement of parents in their children's life can take many forms such as responding to the child's financial need, emotional need, effective communication, creating a home environment that is conducive for

healthy development, social need, and disciplining a child when need calls for it. Vostanis et al (2023) investigated how European adolescent self-concept functions as a predictor for their mental health outcomes. Research findings indicate that self-concept functions as a crucial factor for predicting mental health results in European adolescents. The quality of one's mental health improves as self-concept increases yet diminished self-concept can precipitate worsening mental health conditions Palenzuela-Luis et al. (2022).

Ates (2021) study focused on the significant relationship between parental involvement in education and academic achievement among secondary school students in Turkey. The findings proved that parental involvement contributes to both educational performance and positive student self-concept in secondary school. Vijaya et al. (2016) evaluated the academic achievement patterns between parental engagement and academic performance in higher secondary school students in India. The research established that students' academic success directly correlates with how actively their parents get involved.

Jeynes (2021) studied how African American students' achievement was influenced by parental involvement throughout the United States. They found that students achieved higher educational results when parental involvement reached advanced levels. Hill and Tyson (2020) examined middle school educational participation of parents through multiple strategies that fostered student academic success in the United States. Their findings show particular methods of parental engagement yielded superior results for the academic accomplishments of students.

Kibanda et al (2022) studied the link between self-concept and adolescent mental health in Tanzania. The research findings demonstrated that positive self-concept usually produces excellent mental health results, but negative self-concept triggers multiple mental health concerns. Adeyemi and colleagues (2018) examined parental involvement and support and family education influence on pupil adjustment in lower primary schools located throughout Osun State in Nigeria. Their findings demonstrated that school adjustment relied primarily on high parental involvement according to 36.6% of the respondents, but 26.7% believed moderate involvement was needed, 14.7% required

very high involvement, 18% needed low involvement and 4.3% required very low involvement.

Akinpelu et al (2020) investigated self-concept divergences between male and female secondary school students in Lagos State, Nigeria. The survey findings showed that self-concept levels of male students surpassed those of female students. They established that social norms and gender stereotypes were factors behind the documented differences between men and women. Nnadi (2020) evaluated the role of cultural norms on parental educational involvement across Nigeria. The findings showed that traditional sociocultural beliefs controlled how parents connected with their children's educational activities, demonstrating the importance of cultural knowledge in different settings when developing efficient parental participation approaches.

Musyoka (2019) investigated the role of parental participation on early childhood development education outcomes for learners in Makueni Sub-county, Makueni County, Kenya. Over three-quarters of the head teachers and ECDE teachers strongly concurred that space and lighting limitations negatively impacted numeracy skill development of children; eleven percent of the head teachers and seven and a half percent of the ECDE teachers agreed on the same. Njoki et al (2019) studied the relationship between academic self-concept and Mathematics achievement in secondary schools within Nairobi County Kenya. The study results showed that Mathematics achievement had positive and significant predictions from students' academic self-concept. Most of the existing research focused on specific forms of how parental involvement affects academic performance and discipline with little research on how it affects student's self-concept. Thus, there is a gap in understanding the relationship between different types of parental involvement and the self-concept among students especially in Kiambu County. This study considered other factors that can influence self-concept of students in the study area.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study was to determine the influence of emotional parental involvement on

the self-concept of public secondary school students in Kiambu County, Kenya.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted quantitative correlational research design as the primary method. According to Lawrence (2023) correlational studies evaluate how two or more elements connect to each other. The objective of this research was to determine the influence of emotional parental involvement on self-concept of public secondary school students in Kiambu County, Kenya.

The target population was 3,169 students between 12 to 20 years old, both male and female in public secondary schools in Kiambu County Kenya. A total of five secondary schools participated in the study. Data were collected from 355 students with the assistance of school deputy principals and teachers, who helped organize the students, arrange the setting used, and provide necessary explanations in Swahili to facilitate better understanding of the study by the students.

Robson Self Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) and Parental Involvement Rating Scale (PIRS) were used to collect data, which was then analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Version 25 to generate descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentages) and inferential statistics (Pearson correlation) results. The findings are presented in tables.

Research ethics were observed by obtaining the necessary permissions from The Catholic University of Eastern Africa, the Ministry of

Education, NACOSTI, the County Commissioner, and the principals of the five sampled schools before data collection activities commenced. Participants had the chance to leave the hall before or after the research activities began. A debriefing session was conducted, and participants were appreciated for participating in the study at the completion of data collection. The researchers preserved confidentiality at the highest standards possible throughout the study

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Demographic of the Participants

The study sample consisted of 355 male and female students aged between twelve and twenty years, in five separate public secondary schools in Kiambu County, Kenya. The number of returned surveys was 307, representing 86.55%. The researchers thoroughly investigated the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The background information that was required is age, gender, nature of the parent, nature of the school and level of study of the participants.

Age distribution of Participants

Because age plays a significant role and may affect cognitive ability, the study understand its impact on the relationship between emotional parental involvement and self-concept, it was also deemed a relevant variable in the study. Figure 1 displays the findings of the respondents' age distribution.

Figure 1

Participants' Age Distribution

Figure 1 of the age distribution of the participants revealed that the majority of the sample falls within the 17-18 age range (52.4%, n = 161), followed closely by the 14-16 age range (43.0%, n = 132). The 12-13 age group has the smallest representation (1.0%, n = 3), and the 19-20 age group accounts for 3.6% (n = 11) of the sample.

Gender Distribution of Respondents

The gender of respondent was requested as it was possible that parents had varied expectations, communication patterns and commitments with their sons as compared to daughters which in turn can reflect on the confidence level and in general self-image of students. The gender of the respondents was also analyzed to come up with actual representation of the respondents as to their sex. Figure 2 contains the results of the gender of the respondents.

Figure 2

Gender Distribution of the Participants

Using the Figure 2 data, it is observed that 54.4 percent of the students were females and 45.6 percent were male. Gender did not have any effect on the outcome of the study because both genders were accorded equal chances to participate in the study. The balance between sexes was an urgent issue that the researchers needed to uphold as they knew that social beliefs can bias the participants in the subjective view of the world around them.

Level of Studies of Respondents

This study was carried out in five different public secondary schools with form two, three and four. No form one students because of the new education policy in Kenya. However, to have the right image of the respondent's academic status, the researchers informed about the level of Studies. The distribution of the level of Studies of the participants is in figure 3.

Figure 3
Level of studies of Respondents

Figure 3 indicated that Form 4 students were 107 participants, making a percentage of 34.9%, Form 3 were 103 participants, giving a percentage of 33.6%, and Form 2 were 97 participants, with a percentage of 31.6%.

Types of School

The type of the school of the respondents we examined so that we can come up with the actual picture of the respondents as to the type of school they went to such as: mixed boys' and girls' day, boys boarding and girls boarding. The results of the type of school of the participants are allocated in figure 4.

Figure 4
Type of school

As shown in figure 4, the distribution of participants by type of school indicates that girls boarding schools had the highest representation (37.3%, n = 115), followed by mixed boys and girls day schools (31.6%, n = 97) and boys boarding schools (31.0%, n = 95). These findings suggest a varied distribution of participants across different school types, with Girls' Boarding schools being the most prominent in the study.

Types of Parents

The type of parents that the students were raised will greatly affects emotional parental involvement and self-concept of students. Therefore, to determine the true sentiments of the participants towards their parents, we examined the various forms of parents. Figure 5 showed that the results were scattered based on the type of parents of the participants.

Figure 5

Type of parents of the Participants

Figure 5 revealed that the majority of participants (64.8%, n = 199) lived with both parents. (Father and Mother). This was followed by participants living with their Mother only (22.8%, n = 70). A smaller proportion of participants lived with their Father only (3.0%, n = 9), while 9.4% (n = 29) resided with others. These findings suggest that most participants come from two-parent households, although a significant percentage live in single-parent households, predominantly with their mothers.

Descriptive Statistics of Student Self-Concept

The study sought to establish the self-concept of the participants. Details of the findings are presented in Table 1.

Student Self-Concept

	N	Min i mu m	Maximu m	Mean	Std. Deviation
SELF- CONCEP T	307	1.71	3.74	2.8125	.31333

Valid N (list wise) 307

Table 1

Table 1 findings on the self-concept among the students revealed a moderate level of self-concept, with a mean score of 2.8125. This suggests that, on average, students have a fairly positive self-concept, although there is room for improvement. The standard deviation of 0.31333 indicates that the scores are

relatively consistent, with most students clustering around the mean. Furthermore, the range of scores, from 1.71 to 3.74, highlights the individual differences in self-concept among the students. While some students have relatively low self-concept, others have more positive self-concept. These findings suggest that targeted interventions or programs may be beneficial in enhancing self-concept, particularly for students who struggle with self-concept. The results of this study stand in contrast to earlier studies that emphasize the significance of parental participation in adolescents' academic performance, social and emotional health, and self-perception. Parental participation has been shown to improve student outcomes in studies by Dheivamani et al. (2021), Epstein et al., Hill et al. (2011), Amadhila et al. (2021).

Descriptive Statistics of Parental Emotional Involvement and Student Self-Concept

The study further sought to establish whether parental emotional involvement has any influence on the self-concept of the participants. Details of the findings are presented in Table 2.

Emotional Parental involvement on student self-concept

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
EMOTIONAL INVOLVEMENT	307	1.9489	.22122
SELF-CONCEPT	307	2.8125	.31333
Valid N (list wise)	307		

Table 2

As shown in Table 2, the descriptive statistics revealed that the mean score for Emotional parental Involvement was relatively low (M = 1.9489, SD = 0.22122), indicating that participants generally reported low levels of emotional involvement of their parents. The scores ranged from 1.47 to 2.84, suggesting a narrow range of responses. In contrast, the mean score for Self-Concept was moderate (M = 2.8125, SD = 0.31333), indicating that participants generally had a moderately positive self-concept. The scores ranged from 1.71 to 3.74, suggesting a slightly wider range of responses. The founding's affirmed the reviewed study by Peter (2023) whose result showed students positive self-concept even when their parents were not involved. The literature reviewed by Johnson et al (2021), Thompson et al (2023) , Smith, et al (2022), Specioza (2022) affirmed the vital role of

parental involvement on students self-concept which was not in line with the present study.

Correlation between Emotional Parental Involvement and Self-Concept

The study sought to establish the relationship between emotional parental involvement and the self-concept of the participants. The Pearson correlation was done to determine the relationship between the two variables. Details of the findings are presented in Table 3

Emotional Parental involvement on student self-concept

		EMOTIONAL INVOLVEMENT	SELF-CONCEPT
EMOTIONAL INVOLVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.099
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.082
SELF-CONCEPT	Pearson Correlation	.099	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.082	
	N	307	307

Table 3

DISCUSSION

The results from Table 3 showed that Emotional Involvement related weakly positive to Self-Concept ($r = 0.099$), but the relationship did not show a statistical significance ($p = 0.082$). Such results indicate that Emotional Parental Involvement is not the powerful predictor of Self-Concept, and alternative variables could be more significant. This finding suggests that emotional support is useful, although additional research is necessary to determine that it may have a different effect on self-concept because of other factors.

In addition, the results of this study contrast with the earlier studies which state the importance of parental involvement and emotional support in promoting self-concept and academic performance (Johnson et al., 2021; Thompson et al., 2023; Smith et al., 2022). These studies have indicated that prolonged involvement, emotional support and involvement in school activities have a positive correlation with increased self-concept and academic performance. The gap between the results of the present study and previous investigations can be explained by the

dissimilarities in the research methods, the population, or the particular variables of parental involvement under study. Besides, the findings of the present study suggest that other variables may moderate the effect of emotional parental involvement on self-concept, which should be the topic of future research.

The findings also affirmed the findings by Peter (2023) that students' had positive self-concept even when their parents were not involved. Other studies, Johnson et al (2021), Thompson et al (2023), Smith, et al (2022), Specioza (2022) affirmed the vital role of parental emotional involvement on students' self-concept which was not in line with the present study.

Moreover, the analysis showed an extremely low positive relationship between emotional involvement and self-concept ($r = 0.099$). Nevertheless, this correlation was not significant ($p = 0.082$), and this may indicate that emotional involvement is not a good predictor of self-concept. These findings mean that although emotional support by parents is highly valued, it may not affect self-concept as a sole variable. The reason why this relationship was not significant might show that the relationship between emotional parental involvement and self-concept might be more complex than it was believed; it is possible that other variables might have a more important influence. Such results can be thought to be in conflict to the earlier studies which have laid stress on the necessity of emotional parental involvement in the development of the self-concept of students. Nevertheless, the effect of emotional involvement might be different in terms of peculiarities of personal situations such as the quality of relations between a parent and a child, or the existence of other support systems. The quantitative approach may also have missed out on findings that could have been established using mixed methods.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was concerned with establishing the relationship between emotional parental involvement and self-concept of secondary school students in Kiambu County, Kenya. Results were contrary to the common assumption that emotional parental involvement is a critical factor in influencing the development of the self-concept among students. The relationship between emotional parental involvement, on the one hand, and self-concept, on the other hand, was relatively weak and not statistically significant. The findings indicated that emotional parental involvement may not be a good indicator of self-concept among secondary school learners in this case. The influence of certain other factors like personality traits, relationship with peers, academic

support, or the school environment could be more significant in determining the self-concept of students more effectively. This may also imply the necessity of using both quantitative and qualitative data to better examine factors that affect the development of self-concept.

Further studies should be done to determine the collaboration between emotional parental involvement and other possible predictors of self-concept. A better understanding of these complex relationships will enable educators and parents to devise more effective strategies for developing the positive self-concept of students which is necessary for their academic and general wellbeing.

Conflict of Interest: Authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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